

Study of Hydrophobic Interaction in Binary and Ternary Complexes involving Amino Acids with Non-coordinated Aromatic Groups

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The formation constant of the ternary complexes of the type [MAL], where M=Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}; A=5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-dipyridylamine; and L=3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (dopa), tyrosine, phenylalanine or tryptophan, were determined by potentiometric titration in dioxan-water (1:1, v/v) solution and 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ at 30°. The value of $\Delta \log K$ is found to be positive in all the complexes whereas it is less negative in the Ni^{II} complexes. The enhanced stability of the complex is due to the fact that the hydrophobic free aromatic part of the ligand prefers to be near to the metal ion.

TYROSINE and L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-dopa) are compounds of biochemical importance in the neurotransmission process¹. It is known that tyrosine constitutes terminal part of the peptides enkaphelin and endorphin which regulate the endogenous analgesic activity of the peptides²; and L-dopa is important from both biochemical and therapeutic aspects³⁻⁵.

Dopa is oxidised in the presence of the enzyme dopaoxidase to dopaquinone⁶ which is responsible for oxidising ascorbic acid and also leads to the formation of the black pigment melanine. Dopa is also used as a drug and is administered orally in the treatment of Parkinsonism. However, during the passage through the intestine or liver, dopa is converted into dopamine. The process is catalysed by the enzyme dopacarbonylase. Thus, only a small part of dopa is available for transport to the brain.

It was shown¹ that coordination of L-dopa with metal ion from aminocarboxylate end, reduces the decarboxylation caused by pyridoxal, and hence on administration of Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} complexes of dopa to rat, a greater portion of L-dopa is transported to the brain. Cu^{II} complexes of L-dopa and tyrosine have invited special attention of chemists, as in the synaptosomal fraction of brain Cu^{II} content is high.

L-dopa is also interesting because of its ambidentate nature⁶⁻¹¹. In case of Cu^{II} complex of L-dopa, it has been observed^{1,12} that at lower pH range of 2 to 5, dopa coordinates from aminocarboxylate end. Above pH 6, both aminocarboxylate and pyrocatecholate groups are involved in binding with Cu^{II}, resulting in polymeric species¹³. Above pH 8, two dopa molecules are predominantly bound as catecholates.

It was shown by Rajan and Mainer¹⁴ that in the mixed ligand complex [Cu(2,2'-dipyridyl)(dopa)],

the chelation of dopa is from aminocarboxylate end upto higher pH. It has been further confirmed by us¹⁴ that in [Cu(A)(dopa)] complexes, where A=2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy) or 1,10-phenanthroline (*o*-phen), dopa coordinates from aminocarboxylate end only. The chelation is similar to that in phenylalanine, tyrosine or tryptophan. Though the coordination is from N-O⁻, the value of $\Delta \log K$ has been found to be positive in Cu^{II} complexes and less negative in Ni^{II} complexes.

In view of the above, it was explained that in the ternary complexes [Cu(dipy)(L-dopa)], the presence of free dihydroxyphenyl group in the axial direction of the metal ion, results in the greater stability of the ternary complex¹⁴. It has recently been observed¹⁵ that even in the complexes [Cu(A)-(aromatic amino acids)], where A=aliphatic diamines, there is stabilisation of the ternary complex.

It was shown by Vestues and Martin¹⁶ that the non-coordinated hydrophobic phenyl or substituted phenyl group of amino acids have a preference for position near to the metal ion rather than out in solution. This has been further confirmed by the X-ray analysis of Cu^{II} complexes of tyrosine¹⁷ and dipeptides containing tyrosine or tryptophan groups and Pd^{II} complexes of tyrosine. They exhibit that the aromatic side group is tilted towards the metal ion, with the metal ion-aromatic ring separation less than the van der Waal's contact without bonding through the phenol-OH or indole-NH.

In order to see the effect of substitution on the heteroaromatic N-base A on the ternary complex stability, in the present paper, the study of the mixed ligand complexes [MAL], where M=Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}; A=5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline (A¹) or 2,2'-dipyridylamine (A²); and L=phenylalanine (L¹), tyrosine (L²), L-dopa (L³) or tryptophan (L⁴), has been carried out in 50% dioxan-water medium,

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and the titrations were carried out using a DIGICHEM-8201 digital pH meter with an accuracy of ± 0.01 . In each individual measurement, pH values were corrected for 50% dioxan-water medium by using the method suggested by Uitert and Haas¹⁸.

Calculations were first done considering K_1^H and K_2^H of dopa (L^2) presuming the catechol proton to be undissociated. Calculations were further repeated using K_1^H , K_2^H and K_3^H values of L^3 considering the possibility of one catechol proton dissociation at higher pH. In the second case, the species considered were [MALH] and [MAL] (with one phenolic hydrogen of dopa dissociated). Results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—PROTON ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS AND BINARY STABILITY CONSTANTS IN DIOXAN-WATER (1 : 1, v/v)^a
 $\mu = 0.2 M NaClO_4$, Temp. = 30°

Ligands	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_3^H$	$\log K_{CuL}$	$\log K_{NiL}$
L^1	—	8.81 (± 0.05)	8.11 (± 0.08)	8.57 (± 0.10)	6.02 (± 0.05)
L^2	—	9.17 (± 0.02)	8.4 (± 0.04)	7.59 (± 0.08)	5.88 (± 0.16)
L^3	10.56 (± 0.00)	9.12 (± 0.00)	8.26 (± 0.01)	7.92 (± 0.10)	5.91 (± 0.18)
L^4	—	9.48 (± 0.07)	2.75 (± 0.08)	7.96 (± 0.06)	5.86 (± 0.05)

^a Standard deviation in parenthesis.

TABLE 2—MIXED LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS^a AND ($\Delta \log K$) IN DIOXAN-WATER (1 : 1, v/v)

Ligands	$\log K_{CuA^1L}$	$\log K_{CuA^2L}$	$\log K_{NiA^1L}$	$\log K_{NiA^2L}$
L^1	8.78(± 0.08)	8.45(± 0.08)	5.91(± 0.12)	5.46(± 0.15)
$\Delta \log K$	(+0.21)	(-0.12)	(-0.09)	(-0.56)
L^2	8.87(± 0.10)	8.29(± 0.12)	5.38(± 0.14)	5.03(± 0.12)
$\Delta \log K$	(+1.28)	(+0.70)	(-0.5)	(-0.8)
L^3	9.68(± 0.08)	8.96(± 0.06)	5.42(± 0.10)	5.12(± 0.10)
$\Delta \log K$	(+1.76)	(+1.04)	(-0.49)	(-0.79)
L^4	9.49(± 0.08)	8.92(± 0.08)	6.13(± 0.11)	5.71(± 0.07)
$\Delta \log K$	(+1.59)	(+0.96)	(+0.23)	(-0.15)

^a Standard deviation in parenthesis.

However, there are no significant differences in the values of the formation constants of [MALH] obtained in the two cases, showing that the formation of the species [MAL] is not significant upto pH 8. It should be noted that [MALH] is actually [MALH₂] but is represented as [MALH], as the fourth proton, *i.e.* second undissociated phenolic-OH proton of dopa has not been considered.

The formation constants of the ternary complexes [MAL] were determined by titrating dioxan-water solution (50 ml) of the reactants ([M]-[A]-[L] = 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2) against standard alkali and using the computer program SCOGS¹⁹. Titration of each set was carried out twice to check the

reproducibility of the data. The species present in the solution were considered to be LH₂, LH, L, AH₂, AH, A, Cu^{II}, [CuL]⁺, [CuL₂], [CuA]²⁺, [CuA₂]²⁺ and [CuAL].

Preliminary values of K_{MAL}^{MA} supplied to the computer were obtained by considering the reaction to be of the type²⁰, [CuA] + L \rightleftharpoons [CuAL]. The values of the mixed ligand formation constants obtained by using the two titration data are almost identical and are reported in Table 2.

The concentration plot (Fig. 1) also supports that the complex formation takes place in steps,

Absorption spectral studies : The spectra were recorded on a recording Specord UV/VIS of Carl Zeiss (Jena) spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell using 50% dioxan-water as solvent. Solutions of 10^{-4} and $10^{-5} M$ were used for the uv and visible regions, respectively. Spectra were recorded for free A, free L, [CuA], [CuL₂] and [CuAL] in the pH range where the computer output showed the maximum formation of the species.

Fig. 1. Variation of concentration of different species with pH : (1) free Cu^{II}, (2) [CuA¹] and (3) [CuA¹H, L¹].

Results and Discussion

In cases of phenylalanine and tyrosine, coordination takes place from the aminocarboxylate end of the ligand L, both in [ML] and [MAL] complexes. The single phenolic-OH of tyrosine is less coordinating than the bidentate aminocarboxylate, and hence remains free. As observed earlier^{1,12}, the present investigation also shows that up to pH 5, the dopa coordinates with Cu^{II} from the aminocarboxylate end. At higher pH, dopa is known to coordinate from the catechol end. However, as observed by Rajan *et al.*⁹, the present study also shows that in [CuA dopa], coordination is only

from the aminocarboxylate end of dopa over the pH range 4-8. This is supported by the following observations.

It is interesting to observe the nature of the titration curves of 1:1 Cu-dopa and 1:1:1 or 1:1:10 Cu-A-dopa and to compare with similar cases in Ni^{II} complexes. In Cu-dopa, two buffer regions are observed corresponding to aminocarboxylate coordination at m=0-1 and to catechol coordination at m=1-3, m being the number of moles of base added per mole of total metal ion. In case of Ni-dopa 1:1 solution, only one buffer region is observed at m=0-1, over the whole pH range 4-8, showing coordination only from the aminocarboxylate end.

In the case of both [Cu(A)(dopa)] and [Ni(A)-(dopa)] (Fig. 2), however, only one buffer region is observed between m=0-1 upto pH 8. This shows that the coordination is only from the aminocarboxylate end over the whole pH range. The nature of the titration curve is the same as in case of [M(A)-(phenylalanine)], and [M(A)(tyrosine)] where there is no possibility of coordination from any other site of the secondary ligands. This shows that [CuA] tends to coordinate only from the aminocarboxylate end of dopa. Any coordination from the catechol end should have shown a break at higher pH in [Cu(A)(dopa)].

Fig. 2. Interaction of DOPA with M(II) and (MA¹); M=Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}; M(II)=A=DOPA=1 × 10⁻³ M;

- (1) [NiA¹DOPA] (1:1:1), (2) [NiDOPA] (1:1),
 (3) [CuA¹DOPA] (1:1:1) and (4) [Cu DOPA] (1:1).

This has been further confirmed by the study of the absorption spectra (Table 3) of [Cu(A)-(phenylalanine)], [Cu(A)(tyrosine)], [Cu(A)(dopa)], [Cu(A)(tryptophan)] and comparing with that of [Cu(A)(glycine)]. It is observed that in all three complexes the d-d band occurring at 588.2 nm is similar to that of [Cu(A)(glycine)] (609 nm). This shows that the coordination is from the aminocarboxylate end. Further, in case of [Cu(A)(dopa)], no charge transfer band at 435 nm. a characteristics of phenolic-OH^{1,14} coordination, was observed upto pH 8.

TABLE 3—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF FREE LIGANDS, BINARY AND MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES IN DIOXAN-WATER (1:1, v/v)

Compd.	λ_{max} (nm)
5-Nitro-1,10-phen(A ¹)	207.5, 227.8, 263.2
Phenylalanine (L ¹)	208.3
Tyrosine (L ²)	222.2, 277.8
Dopa (L ³)	281.7
[Cu ^I A ₂ ¹]	216.5, 279.3, 719.4
[Cu ^I L ₂ ¹]	223.5, 275.9, 625
[Cu ^{II} L ₂ ²]	208.3, 288.1, 625
[Cu ^{II} L ₂ ³]	222.2, 283.3, 312.5, 434, 625
[Cu ^{II} A ¹ L ¹]	261.7, 277.7, 340.1, 588.2
[Cu ^{II} A ¹ L ²]	222.2, 279.3, 344.8, 588.2
[Cu ^{II} A ¹ L ³]	222.2, 279.3, 342.4, 588.2

Hence, in the refinement of the formation constant values of log K_{CuAdopa}^{CuAdopa} by the computer program, dopa has been considered to coordinate with [CuA] from the aminocarboxylate end throughout. The ternary complex species considered was [CuAH₂L³], uncoordinated OH groups being undissociated and reproducible results were obtained in each case. No convergence was obtained when species with catechol coordination were considered. It can be explained as follows. In the lower pH range, dopa coordinates with [CuA] from aminocarboxylate end. The formation of dimeric species through catechol coordination cannot take place because the other two equatorial coordination positions are occupied by 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline or dopa in [Cu(A)(dopa)]. Phenolate O⁻ cannot displace the coordinated aminocarboxylate even at higher pH because the substitution of electron withdrawing group over the ring reduces coordinating tendency of dopa phenolate O⁻ with [CuA]. Hence, the [CuAH₂L³] complex with aminocarboxylate coordination is retained upto higher pH. The free phenolate O⁻ do not coordinate at the fifth and sixth position of Cu^{II} of another molecule, probably because Cu^{II} does not favour axial coordination.

An interesting aspect is the higher stability of phenylalanine, tyrosine, L-dopa, tryptophan ternary complexes as compared to glycine one. Normally in [CuAL] complexes, where L coordinates through N-O⁻, value of $\Delta \log K$ is negative²¹. However, in all the present complexes studied, though the coordination of L is from aminocarboxylate end, the value of $\Delta \log K$ is more positive in case of Cu^{II}

TABLE 4—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES IN DIOXAN-WATER (1 : 3, 1 : 1, v/v)*
 $\mu = 0.2 M NaClO_4$, Temp. = 30°

Solvent	$\log K_{CuA^2L}$			$\log K_{NiA^2L}$		
	L ¹	L ²	L ³	L ¹	L ²	L ³
Dioxan-water (1 : 3, v/v)	8.29 (±0.08)	8.96 (±0.1)	9.66 (±0.1)	5.18 (±0.14)	5.90 (±0.1)	6.02 (±0.13)
$\Delta \log K$	+0.26	+1.05	+1.47	-0.26	+0.17	+0.42
Dioxan-water (1 : 1, v/v)	8.45 (±0.03)	8.29 (±0.12)	8.92 (±0.08)	5.46 (±0.15)	5.08 (±0.12)	5.71 (±0.07)
$\Delta \log K$	-0.12	+0.70	+0.96	-0.56	-0.8	-0.15

* Standard deviation $\sigma\beta$ in parenthesis.

complexes and only small negative in case of Ni^{II} complexes.

The higher formation constants for these complexes are explained by considering that the aminocarboxylate end of phenylalanine, tyrosine, tryptophan or L-dopa coordinates with [CuA] and the phenyl, phenol or catechol part remains free. It may be expected to spread over the heteroaromatic N-base part of A, leading to an intra-molecular stacking interaction between the tertiary amines and the aromatic ring of the secondary ligand as suggested^{22,23} in case of [Cu^{II}(*o*-phen)-(phenylacetate)] complex.

Sook-Hui and Martin²⁴ have also observed that both aliphatic and aromatic unidentate amines bind more strongly to the dipeptide complex with a phenylalanine side chain suggesting a hydrophobic interaction between the phenyl group and hydrocarbon portions of the amine. The hydrophobic interaction is possible probably because the amine is unidentate and longer chained. In case of the present [CuAL] complexes, however, construction of model shows that the aromatic ring of the amino acid can spread only over the axial region of Cu^{II} and not beyond. This makes intra-molecular inter-ligand interaction less likely. Odani and Yamauchi¹⁵ also did not consider hydrophobic interaction between ethylenediamine and substituted ethylenediamine and the free aromatic part of the amino acid. They explained the greater stability of the [Cu(diamine)(amino acid)] ternary complex by considering the shift of electrons from metal ion to the aromatic ring of the amino acid. This facilitates the coordination of the second ligand stabilising the ternary complex. However, the interaction of the free aliphatic part of the amino acid is not so strong with the metal ions. Moreover, if there is electron shift from metal ion to the amino acid, it should facilitate the attachment of a σ bonding aliphatic diamine more than σ and π bonding aromatic diamine. However, in the present study, it is seen that $\Delta \log K$ is positive in [Cu(A)(aromatic amino acid)], whereas it is negative in [Cu(en)(aromatic amino acid)] as observed by Odani and Yamauchi¹⁵.

The enhanced stability of these complexes can be explained by considering that the hydrophobicity

of the metal environment increases on coordination with an aromatic N-base. It is well known that the environment of metal porphyrin is highly hydrophobic. Hence, the interaction of [CuA] with the phenyl or hydroxyphenyl group is more, consequently, the ligand L is more strongly bound with [CuA] than [Cu(H₂O)₂] resulting in more stable ternary complex. This leads to positive $\Delta \log K$ in Cu^{II} complexes and less negative $\Delta \log K$ in Ni^{II} complexes. The stability of the complex [CuA'L] is found to be much greater than [Cu(phen)(L)]²⁵ due to the presence of the electron withdrawing nitro group over A'. This depletes the electron density over the ring, making it a stronger π acid than 1,10-phenanthroline and hence, stabilises the ternary complexes. In case of dopa, an electron donating imino (NH) group attached between the two pyridine moieties enhances the electron density on the ring due to the presence of a lone-pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom. However, the delocalisation of electron density in dopa is over a larger area than in 2,2'-dipyridyl. Hence, the values of the ternary complex stability are comparable for [CuAL], with A=dipyridyl or dipyrindyl amine.

It is interesting to observe the effect of the solvent composition (Table 4). With increasing dioxan concentration, the $\Delta \log K$ value becomes less positive. This is probably because the non-aqueous solvent comes in between the metal ion and the free aromatic group and lowers the metal aromatic ring hydrophobic interaction.

Such a study is of biochemical importance as the ligands A are similar to imidazole which is an essential constituent of histamine, abundant in biochemical system. Coordination of L-dopa is restricted to aminocarboxylate end in [Cu(A)(dopa)] type of complexes and coordination with [CuA] results in the formation of a stable complex leading to inhibition of dopa or tyrosine decarboxylation. Moreover, solvent effect is of significance, because biological fluids have different composition.

References

1. K. S. RAJAN, S. MAINER and J. M. DAVIS, *Bioinorg. Chem.*, 1978, 9, 187.

2. O. YAMAUCHI, K. TSUJIDE and A. ODANI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 659.
3. K. S. RAJAN, S. MAINER and J. M. DAVIS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 2089.
4. T. KISS and A. GERGELY, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **78**, 247.
5. J. B. SUMMER and K. MYRBACK, "The Enzymes", Academic Press, New York, 1951, Vol. 2, Part 1, p. 489.
6. J. E. GORTON and R. F. JAMESON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2615.
7. J. E. GORTON and R. F. JAMESON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1972, 804.
8. J. E. GORTON and R. F. JAMESON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1972, 310.
9. WHEI-HU-KWICK, E. PURDY and E. I. STIEFEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 1638.
10. J. R. PILLROW, S. G. CARR and T. D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 723.
11. S. G. CARR, T. D. SMITH and J. R. PILLROW, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 2569.
12. K. S. RAJAN, A. A. MANIAN, J. M. DAVIS and H. DEKIMEJIAN, *Brain Res*, 1976, **107**, 317.
13. R. K. BOGGESS and R. B. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 3076.
14. V. K. PATEL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1984, **1**, 20.
15. A. ODANI and O. YAMAUCHI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **13**, 93.
16. P. I. VESTUES and R. B. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 7906.
17. D. V. D. HELM and C. E. TATSCH, *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. B*, 1972, **28**, 2307.
18. L. G. VAN UITERT and L. G. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
19. I. G. SAYCE, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1897; 1971, **18**, 651; I. G. SAYCE and V. S. SHARMA, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 831.
20. K. GOPALKRISHNAN and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1982, 353.
21. R. GRIESSER and H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 1238.
22. H. SIGEL, in "Advances in Solution Chemistry", eds. I. BERTINI, L. LUNAZZING and E. A. DIET, 1981, p. 149.
23. M. B. RAMAN, K. H. SCHELLER, H. ULRICH, R. TRIBOLET and H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 2067.
24. KIM SOOK-HUI and R. B. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 1707.
25. N. EMANUEL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 596.